

Trusted Smart Surveys: a possible application of Privacy Enhancing Technologies in Official Statistics

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Abstract In this discussion paper we outline the general concept of Trusted Smart Surveys as a possible use-case for the application of Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PET). Central to the Trusted Smart Survey paradigm is the notion of *extracting output information without revealing the input data*. This can be achieved by leveraging PET to compute the final desired information — a statistical indicator or an aggregate table — without centralising the individual data from the respondents. Together with additional mechanisms for ensuring transparency, auditability and public control over the whole process these technologies can help to scale up public trust in new survey models, hence promoting participation, and in this way contribute to improve accuracy and relevance of official statistics.

Key words: Trusted Smart Survey, Trusted Smart Statistics, Privacy Enhancing Technologies, Official Statistics.

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1 From traditional surveys to Smart Surveys

The traditional survey model based on paper questionnaire is based on a batch of questions (questionnaire) presented to the respondent, by a human interviewer, during a single survey session. Such questionnaire-based interaction model has not changed with telephone-based and computer-assisted interviews. Instead, leveraging the smartphone (via a mobile app) allows for several important changes to the survey model. First, the so-called *response burden* can be diluted over much longer intervals, even months or years, with a continuous flow of questions presented at very low rate in the background of the respondent's normal activities. Second, the *active data* generated in response to explicit queries may be complemented by and combined with *passive data* collected automatically by sensors onboard the smartphone (e.g. GPS, accelerometer, etc.) or acquired from other devices within the personal sphere of the respondent (e.g., home appliances, Internet-of-Things devices), again contributing to reduce the response burden (e.g., automatic diary). Third, the human interviewer can be replaced by an Artificial Intelligence (AI) assistant. The combination of these elements enable the design of *context-aware* survey models where *timing and content* of the presented questions are decided dynamically based on *context* information as inferred based on the sensor data. For example, a question of the kind "*It seems you are travelling today: is this trip mainly intended for work or for leisure?*" might be posed during the trip instead of the more traditional "*How many business trips did you perform in the previous 6 months?*" In other words, the combined use of AI and passive data allow to decide dynamically *when* and *what* question to ask. Furthermore, questions can request explicit action and non-textual response, for example taking photos or recording sound ("*Can you please take a photo of your surrounding environment?*").

What we have outlined insofar is basically the concept of *Smart Surveys*. Through the smartphone app, Statistical Offices (SO) have the possibility to establish a continuous, long-term dialogue with each respondent. Furthermore, they have the opportunity to feed back individualised reports to the respondent, to disseminate selected figures and statistics of special interest for particular groups, and to better communicate the importance of official statistics. In this way, the bi-directional dialogue between the SO and the respondent may become even more interactive.

Such fundamental change of paradigm is enabled not only by the availability of mobile technologies, but also by the fact that continuous interaction with mobile apps is considered rather normal nowadays. It is not only a matter of exploiting *new digital technologies*, but also leveraging the *new digital behaviours* and *new digital attitudes* that citizens have developed through the use of such technologies. In the private sector, marketing strategies are increasingly relying on continuous low-intensity interaction with customers via mobile apps, and in principle similar practices (with appropriate adaptations) may be adopted by public institutions for public interest purposes, including by statistical offices to produce better official statistics. That does not mean that SOs are called to emulate marketing practices from the commercial sector. Rather on the contrary, SOs have the opportunity to pioneer new models of data use based on their constituent principles of transparency,

openness, independence and democratic control, and to *show the way* to other public institutions (but also to the private sector) as to how the collectivity can (re)gain democratic control over its data. In so doing, SO should remain critical and vigilant of the possible negative consequences and unintended effects, not least the risk of distorting — or anyway influencing excessively — the social phenomena they aim at measuring. Taking a critical design approach, SO can design new survey models that ripe the potential benefits of the new (data, technologies, behaviours, attitudes) while minimising the potential risks. In the remainder of this short contribution we propose an initial reflection on one of several aspects related to the design of a suitable Smart Survey model, namely the issue of *trust*.

2 From Smart Surveys to *Trusted Smart Surveys*

The *smart survey* model is considerably more intrusive in the life of the participant than the traditional survey model: it would allow SO to plug into a much richer, wider and deeper set of data about the individual respondent and his/her activities, with much greater level of detail and for longer times. The rising awareness by the public about the dystopian risks of mass surveillance would make such model difficult to accept (if at all desirable) unless a set of convincing safeguards are put in place to offset the risks of any possible data misuse — against the individuals, groups and the whole collectivity — and to guarantee a level of transparency and *trustworthiness* that is commensurate to the risks.

Trust is a complex issue where aspects of *trust in the process*, *trust in the input data* and *trust in the output statistics* are closely intermingled and reciprocally inter-dependent. If the respondents fear negative consequences resulting from participating in Smart Surveys, they will not provide their truthful data (or provide no data at all) and the resulting final figures will be poorly representative of reality. In this way, lack of trust in the process causes lack of trust in the input data and therefore in the final statistics. To stir a virtuous cycle of trust, SOs must provide strong trust guarantees on the whole survey process in the first place.

As the survey model evolves from traditional to smart, additional guarantees must be provided, also based on new technological means. The success of a well designed Smart Survey model requires SOs to put in place (and convincingly communicate to the respondents and to the general public) a set of strong mechanisms to ensure *by design* public control on *what information is extracted* from such data, *how* (methodology), *why* (purpose) and *by whom*. This requires the deployment of a coherent combination of “soft” measures (i.e. legal provisions, organisational processes, practices) and “hard” measures (i.e. technological solutions) that are adequate to the new scenario¹. Putting in place a coherent set of strong safeguards is what qualifies the *Trusted Smart Survey* model, i.e., an augmentation of the Smart

¹ While a set of measures is already in place to ensure trustworthiness of statistical production and protection of personal data collected from traditional sources, such measures need to be scaled up and strengthened in order to cope with new, more intrusive non-traditional kinds of data sources.

Survey concept by technological and non-technological elements aimed at increasing the degree of *trustworthiness of data use*.

3 Design principles: an initial proposal

Designing a Trusted Smart Survey model is a task that involves multiple dimensions: it is matter of *trustworthiness engineering* where security, privacy, organisational and communication elements must be blended together, each of them entailing hardware, software and *humanware* aspects. To this aim, it is important to establish a common terminology and a clear set of design principles and requirements in the first place. A key aspect of the Trusted Smart Survey paradigm, and more in general of the whole Trusted Smart Statistics concept [1], is a shift of focus from *data collection* to *data use*. This implies that the central pivot of the whole engineering process is the *combination of DATA and CODE* — not merely DATA.

Generally speaking, given a collection of input data x and pre-defined function f , statistical production entails the computation of the output $y = f(x)$. The *function* f denotes here any generic algorithmic workflow (or statistical methodology) described by a pre-defined sequence of mathematical operations of arbitrary complexity. The most complete and non-ambiguous description of a complex function f is by means of a computer program, i.e., software code. A computation instance, or *query*, is therefore associated to the application of CODE f to DATA x , hence to the DATA-CODE pair $\langle x, f \rangle$. Both elements may be centralised at a single machine administered by a single entity, or distributed among multiple machines possibly administered by different entities. In the envisioned model of Trusted Smart Survey the individual data of each participant remain local to the participant's private space (e.g., her personal device or private cloud space). The code execution is split between the participant's machine, for the local pre-processing of individual data ("micro" processing), and an institutional or inter-institutional infrastructure supporting secure private computation of aggregate values ("macro" processing) through PET. Such PET infrastructure might possibly comprise multiple machines administered by different organisations, as e.g. with Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), or it may reduce to a single machine controlled jointly by multiple institutions, e.g., based on Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) combined with mechanisms for multi-party authorisation. Whatever PET solution is adopted, it is important to avoid concentrating control into a *single point of trust*.

Paraphrasing a famous quote: "*DATA is neither good nor bad; nor is it neutral*" (the original version had "technology" instead of "data" [2]). In fact, the discourse about what is ethically desirable vs. undesirable — hence operationally allowed or disallowed, technically enabled vs. disabled — would be more clearly scoped if centered specifically on the DATA-CODE pair $\langle x, f \rangle$, rather than solely on DATA x . It is possible to envision data governance models wherein the legal right *and the technical possibility* of applying a particular CODE on a particular set of DATA is

decoupled from who holds the data. Keeping data holding and data usage as distinct issues is indeed a pivotal aspect in the discourse.

Based on the above considerations, we list below a possible set of design principles for the future Trusted Smart Survey model. Our goal here is to present an initial proposal serving as starting point for a critical discussion within the statistical community. With the caveat above, we propose to consider the following design principles:

1. For a generic respondent i , the individual data element x_i remains private to the respondent and is never disclosed as such to any single other entity — DATA are closed and remain stored at their respective sources.
2. The source code of f is always made openly available for public scrutiny *before* and *after* performing the computation, in order to allow for ex-ante and ex-post checks — CODE is open.
3. The final result of the computation y (query output) is made available to the SO but not automatically released to the public — access to the query output remains restricted to authorised SO.
4. Before execution, the source code of f must be approved by a pre-determined set of ex-ante controllers.
5. The execution of every query must be logged in a secure way and made accessible to ex-post controllers. Each log must contain all appropriate meta-data, including an unmodifiable pointer to the exact code version that was executed and detailed information as to who had access to the computation result.
6. Technical and organisation means are adopted to ensure that the binary (executable) code run on the data corresponds to the (source) code f that was preliminarily approved by *all* ex-ante controllers (e.g., code authentication).
7. Technical and organisation means are adopted to ensure that the information stored in every log corresponds truthfully to the query execution.

The role of ex-ante or ex-post controller may be taken by any entity (institution, organisation, association, etc.) bearing a legally recognised interest related to the query. To illustrate, consider the example that entity A is mandated to ensure methodological quality (the code f is appropriate and fit for the purpose), entity B cares that the prospective output to be computed by f is ethically acceptable, and entity C is concerned that the same output does not cause harm to some legitimate private business. One possible way to reassure and gain support by all entities is to assign to all such entities a *shared, non-exclusive* ex-ante controller role. Similar considerations apply for the assignment of ex-post controller roles. We do not claim here that each and every entity with some interest in the computation has automatically the right to act as controller. However, the PET infrastructures must allow to flexibly configure ex-ante and ex-post controller roles to different entities as needed in each specific use-case. In other words, having such feature in place at the software and hardware level allows to flexibly engineer the process and governance model at the *humanware* level, and to assign shared, non-exclusive controls to the relevant and legitimate stakeholders.

Note that Principle (3) foresees that access to the computation output \mathbf{y} may still be restricted to the SO. This provision allows to execution of computation function \mathbf{f} for which the output \mathbf{y} still yields some residual risk of personal re-identification. In this case, it is responsibility of the SO to apply the usual Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) checks in post-processing before releasing the final statistics to the public. Alternatively, Differential Privacy (DP) mechanisms may be embedded in the computation function \mathbf{f} . Depending on the specific use-case, both variants can be considered. In summary, referring to the notions of Input Privacy and Output Privacy (see e.g. to [3] for a discussion), the whole chain from raw input data until final statistics must compose an Input Privacy solution (e.g., SMPC or TEE) with a solution for Output Privacy (SDC or DP).

The above principles imply that (i) the computation function \mathbf{f} is defined beforehand, and (ii) the whole statistical production process is fully automatized and represented in machine-readable code. These conditions are not problematic in the statistical *production* stage, but may be somewhat critical for *research* and *methodological development* where some degree of manual data exploration is unavoidably needed. To cope with such situation, a slightly modified set of design principles could be formulated, where some items are loosened (e.g., ex-ante checks) while others are strengthened (e.g., ex-post checks) in order to maintain adequate control while allowing for the necessary degree of flexibility during manual exploration.

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